

Review On Stabilization of Soil Using Sugarcane Baggase Ash and Polypropylene Fibres for Rigid Pavement

¹Priyanka Nagdeve, ²Shivali Dhanorkar, ³Sanjana Motghare, ⁴Prof. Pankaj N. Patil

Abstract— Mainly we studied how to improve the quality of foundation soil. For our project work, we reviewed many research papers, and from that, we noted that for effective stabilization of soil, there should be an improvement in the chemical properties of soil and physical properties of soil. Many use fibers to improve the physical strength of soil, these fibers have to be strong enough and have high tensile resistance properties. i.e. Coir fiber, bamboo fiber, glass fiber, polypropylene fiber. For improvement in Chemical properties, they used cementitious material for increasing binding strength. i.e. fly ash, silica fume, company kiln dust, sugarcane baggase ash. The combination of fibers and binding materials is very useful for the improvement of the strength of soil, hence from this we need to take one binding material and one fibre to get positive results. These all are taken at different proportion to get optimum content. Also, we need to select some test to verify changes.

Keywords— Sandy Silty Soil, Clay Soil, Virgin Soil, Pavment.

I. INTRODUCTION

For any civil engineering structure strong enough to bear load on it. In India there are several types of soil found, some are strong enough which is mostly stabilized naturally, some are agriculture friendly and some are not so strong enough but also infertile. When we want to construct there are many problematic soils occurs. Due to low quality soil, there is need to build much strong superstructure. For strong base the soil needs to be stabilized.

Fibres use in soil stabilization which can be act as a reinforcement for soil. Fibres distribute the load on large area. There should be use of binding materials such cement, fly ash

and sugarcane baggase ash. The combination of these two mixed with soil. The stabilize soil can be use for pavement construction to reduce thickness for rigid pavement.

II. OBJECTIVES

- Need of waste factory materials or other waste material for construction purpose.
- To know that waste materials are used for mixing in soil means reduced the cost of construction work.
- Need of stabilization improves the strength of concrete that directly tend to reduced thickness of pavement.
- Need to reduce solid waste because the solid waste is major problem nowadays, that's why we try to use it in construction purpose.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ajay goyal (2007) et al. They done the examination on the RSA (Rice straw Ash). They find the nature of Ash higher consuming temperature. These are material and they directed the test and know the tantamount compressive and flexural quality of the mortar in the wake of blending this material. Finishing the testing they found that improve the quality of the mortar due to siliceous, aluminous and etc. properties of the material.

Akansa Gautam (2018) et al. Studied to enhancing the properties of black cotton soil by utilizing bagasse ash and coir fiber. It is noted that addition of 10% sugarcane waste and 4% coir fiber in soil gave the strength in the specimen. Similarly, The CBR value rise new CBR value of the test specimen in 2.5 mm penetration in the submerged and un-submerged soil is 6.31 and 14.93 respectively. The percentage increase in new CBR value for 2.5 mm penetration in submerged and un- submerged is recorded as 52.42% and 159.65%.

Amit S. Kharade, (2014) et al. They researched that the expansive soil can be stabilized by using bagasse ash. Various experiments were done on samples during this research. For stabilizing expansive (black cotton) soil, The partial replacement of soil with bagasse ash at the rate 3%, 6%, 9% and 12% is done. At 06% of replacement of soil with bagasse

Manuscript Received May 5, 2024; Revised 15 May, 2024 and Published on May 30, 2024

Pro Priyanka Nagdeve, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: priyanka.kalamar1984@gmail.com

Shivali Dhanorkar, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id:

Sanjana Motghare, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id:

Prof. Pankaj N. Patil, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.

ash without any addition of chemicals and binding material showed very high rise in properties of black cotton soil. For getting the optimum value at which soil stabilized, standard proctor test and UCS test were conducted. Chittaranjan et al. The subgrade soil which is not stabilized is treated with over three wastes independently at 0%, 03%, 06%, 09%, 12% and 15% and CBR test is done for each percent. Increase in the percentage of agricultural waste in soil showed increase in CBR value of the test samples.

Amu, S (2011) et al. They led the testing on the essential properties of the dirt by blending sugar bagasse Ash as stabilizer. the diverse test performed reason that California Bearing Ratio test, explicit gravity and dampness content. Here the dirt utilized is lateric soil. The siliceous and aluminous properties having the cementeous quality at a specific warm effect. PI of the dirt abatements for various examples which show the dirt improvement. CBR is additionally increments higher % regarding unique sample. UCS is the fundamental property of the clayey soil. The end is that subsequent to blending sugar bagasse Ash brilliant outcomes found in expanding the quality of the dirt.

Dr. Siddhartha Rokade (2017) et al. Their study is about addition of nylon fibre along with fly ash to measure the change in the strength parameters of black cotton soil. The CBR of the soil was determined by conducting three series of tests. Tests were carried out on the BC soil mixed with varying percentage of fly ash, from 10% to 40% out of which 20% came out to be optimum. Then, nylon fibre with aspect ratios (length/ diameter) 20, 40, 60 and 80 and fiber contents were varied from 0.25% to 1.5% with 0.25% interval, out of which 0.75% of fibre content is the considered as optimum on the basis of MDD and maximum CBR value

Haider Hassan (aym2016) et al. They did his research on bagasse ash. the Bagasse ash is a fibrous material which consists of high amount of silica. which is considered as pozzolanic material having non-reactive nature and can possibly be utilized for stabilizing the road subgrade. So as to exhibit the potential capacity of the bagasse ash in reducing the unfriendly impacts of expansive soils on roads, a cluster of exploratory tests utilizing bagasse ash were directed. In their investigation bagasse ash & hydrated lime was utilized and mixed in with black soil tests, gathered from Queensland, Australia. Test specimens were made by utilizing various % of bagasse ash and hydrated lime i.e. 0%, 06%, 10%, 18% & 25% by the dry mass of soil, at a proportion of 3:1 respectively. The outcomes of UCS test, CBR test and FSR test were introduced for untreated and treated soil samples after different curing period of 3 days, 7 Days and 28 days. The results of these tests obviously showed that the adjustment of expansive soils utilizing hydrated lime and bagasse ash improves the quality as well as encourages adapting to ecological worries through decrease of sugar free.

7. John Paul V (2016) et al. They used bamboo fiber on quality conduct of fly ash treated black cotton soil. This paper done on the compaction and quality conduct of fly ash treated expansive soil with bamboo fiber. The idealy fly ash was seen as 20% by load of soil. Bamboo fiber of the normal width 0.45 mm and 25 mm length are utilized. It was arbitrarily included into the fly ash treated as soil at four unique rates of fiber content. The fortified soil tests were conducts unconfined pressure test and compaction tests. It is proven that quality properties of ideal mix of Black cotton soil-fly ash with bamboo filaments is considerably better than untreated black cotton soil.

Kameshwar Rao Tallapragada (2009) et al. They works on benefits of fiber reinforced subgrade. They taken two fibres: nylon fibre and monofilament. The main tests performed were CBR test & UCS test to check the strength. Three proportions were prepared as 0.75%, 1.5% & 2.25%. Their result shows that CBR value of Black Cotton soil also increases considerably due to addition of fibers in soil. From UCS test it was found that Maximum Stress value of soil increases with increasing aspect ratio of nylon fibre.

Ken C. Onyelowe (2012) et al. They had done the study on Akwete Lateritic Soil stabilized with cement and Bagasse Ash that was taken from 1.5m below the top layer of soil. In this study soil was stabilized by adding 4% and 6% of cement with the addition of bagasse ash in varying percentage at the rate 0%, 02%,04%, 06%, 08% and 10% by weight of dry soil. After mixing in the soil various tests were performed ie. OMC, MDD and CBR. After sometime it is concluded that with the increase in bagasse ash, OMC also increased. It was observed that the addition of bagasse ash improved the CBR value in comparison to the natural soil. MDD reduced at the 4% of cement with bagasse ash in soil where as MDD increased at 6% of cement content with the increase in the actual percentage of bagasse ash.

M.Heeralal (2011) et al. They Studied the effect of Polypropylene fibre on CKD stabilized soil. The soil they used is Black cotton soil and the various proportions of CKD were 3%, 5%, & 8%. The proportions of PP fibre were taken as 0.25%, 0.50% & 1%. UCS test and CBR test were conducted and the value of both UCS test and CBR test was maximum at CKD content of 8% and fibre content of 1%. So this proportion was considered to be optimum.

Figure 1: Steps of Proposed Method

CONCLUSION

- We reviewed that increase the pavement compressive strength and reduce optimum moisture content.
- We also reviewed that increases the density of soil by using material like fibres and binding materials.
- We reviewed that optimum content of fibre and cementitious material tend to reduce the pavement thickness.
- We reviewed that optimum content of binding materials in soil such as sugarcane baggase ash, fly ash and CKD are nearly 20%.
- We also reviewed that optimum content of Fibre in soil, such as bamboo fibre, coir fibre, polypropylene fibre and glass fibres are nearly taken as 1%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ajay goyal, Hattori kunio, Hidehiko ogata, Monika garg, A.M. Anwar, M. Ashraf and mandala" Synergic effect of Rice straw ash and rice-Straw ash on strength properties of mortar", 2007, Journal of applied sciences 7 (21): 3256-3261.
- [2] Amu, S. A Oguniyi and O.O Oladeji, Geotechnica properties of Lateritic Soil Stabilized with sugar cane straw ash, America Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research, 2011, 2(2), pp. 323-339.
- [3] Dr. Siddhartha Rokade, Rakesh Kumar, Dr. P.K. Jain(2017) "Effect of Inclusion of Fly-Ash and Nylon Fiber on Strength Characteristics of Black Cotton Soil". EJGE Vol. 22 [2017].
- [4] Hayder Hassan, Leit Dang, Hadi Khabbaz, behzad Fatehi, Sergei Terzaghi "Remediation of expansive soil using agricultural waste Bagasse Ash" International Conference on Transportation Geo techniques, vol. 143, pp. 1368-1375, 2016.
- [5] John Paul V, Antony Rachel Sneha M. "effect of random inclusion of the hamboo fibre on strength behavior of fly ash treated black cotton soil" int. j. of civil eng and technol, 2016. Vol 7 issue 5, pp 153-160.©2020, IRJET | Impact Factor value: 7.529 | ISO 9001:2008 Certified Journal | Page 3882.
- [6] M.Heeralal, G.V. Praveen (2011) "A study on effect of fiber on cement kiln dust stabilized soil". JERS/Vol. II/ Issue 2011/173-177 IV/October-December.
- [7] Kameshwar Rao Tallapragada, Anuj Kumar Sharma, Tarulata Meshram (2009) "laboratory investigation of use of synthetic fibers to minimize swell in expansive subgrades". IGC 2009, Guntur, INDIA.
- [8] Ken C. Onyelowe "Cement Stabilized Akwueze Lateritic Soil and the Use of Bagasse Ash as Admixture" International Journal of Science and Engineering Investigations, 2012 vol. 1, issue 2.,